

Japanese gardens and traditions

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Abstract: This article covers the maashhur gardens of Japan, the peculiarities of their nature, Customs and traditions. It is believed that through the beauty of nature, a person knows himself, and his thinking has a noble effect on the world of the human soul. In the process of building a Japanese garden, according to Oriental legends, many centuries-old trees with living spirit and energy were preserved. Also on the territory of the garden there are sakura trees - decorative cherries, the observation of their flowering is an integral part of Japanese culture.

Key words: japanese gardens, contemplation, landscape, country, world, universe, art, special, beauty, philosophical, universe, mountain, sky, plant, tea.

Japan is considered one of the most exotic, ancient and spiritually rich countries in the world. In Japanese culture, Gardens occupy a special place – a philosophical-moral concept of the universe and a special type of art that skillfully harmonizes the natural beauty of the landscape. Guests of the "self-Center" MKM have a unique opportunity to visit a real Japanese garden, created in the best traditions of the country of Sunrise. It is believed that through the beauty of nature, a person knows himself, and his thinking has a noble effect on the world of the human soul. In the process of building a Japanese garden, according to Oriental legends, many centuries-old trees with living spirit and energy were preserved. Also on the territory of the garden there are sakura trees - decorative cherries, the observation of their flowering is an integral part of Japanese culture.

There is a special art of stone laying in the land of the Rising Sun, which is known as Sute-Ishi. The Japanese believe that by following the example of Buddhist monks and thinking about a stone garden, it is possible to influence the innermost secrets of the universe, know one's own soul and achieve wisdom. The "Sekitei" garden, located on the territory of the Japanese garden, was created in accordance with the traditions of the 14th century of the Zen Buddhist era. Carefully selected and correctly placed stones form compositions full of deep philosophical meaning, which attract

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF 2024 = 5.073/Volume-2, Issue-7

those who seek natural peace and tranquility. The Japanese garden, started by the First Temple Gardens founded by Buddhist monks and pilgrims, gradually began to form a whole beautiful and complex system of art. In 794, the Japanese capital was moved from Nara to Kyoto. The first Gardens looked like places for holidays, games and concerts under the open sky. The gardens of this period are a unique decoration. They are planted with many flowering trees (plum, cherry), musculature, as well as climbing Glycinia plants. However, Japan also has unkempt gardens created from stone and sand. In artistic design, they look like abstract paintings. The Japanese Garden symbolizes the perfect world of nature on Earth and sometimes acts as the embodiment of the Universe. Characteristic elements of his composition are artificial mountains and hills, islands, rivers and waterfalls, sand or gravel paths and places decorated with stones of an unusual shape. The landscape of the garden is formed by trees, shrubs, bamboos, grasses, beautifully flowering plants and mosses. The formation of the foundations of Japanese gardening took place under the influence of the evolution of Japanese architecture as well as the religious-philosophical ideas of the Japanese nobility. Initially, the garden was an integral part of aristocratic residences, but was later borrowed by Buddhist monasteries and noble samurai. Since the 19th century, it has become widespread among the Japanese commoners and an integral part of many private houses. The construction of Japanese-style gardens in the 20th century also became popular outside Japan. The three most famous parks in Japan are traditionally Kenroku-en (Kanazawa), Koraku-en (Okayama), and Kayraku-en (Mito).

In a Japanese Garden, the placement of composite units is carried out according to the relief so that they form a whole. The system of placement of elements is based on the laws of nature, transformed into the laws of harmony, implemented and developed in the process of long analysis of natural and artificial analogs. The approach to the placement of elements depends on the purpose of creating a garden: to enjoy thinking in static mode, when viewing points are moving inside and outside pavilions, in a boat or around a reservoir, surrounded by bright pictures that are often exchanged.

Blue tea and Japanese tea – these sound like meaningless with each other. Blue tea is considered the most popular drink in Japan and a piece of values, again seeing it as good for health as well. The presence of freshly brewed blue tea on the table after a meal has become commonplace in a sunflower land. In Japan, varieties differ depending on the variety of tea production, drying, and other processes involved, or the

taste, color, flavor, aroma of the tea. Sencha is the most commonly consumed type of tea in Japan. It is made only from young tea leaves. Tea leaves are picked, washed, steamed, and then dried. Matcha tea, which is characterized by its lush greenery, is grown in the shade. With this, the aim is to increase the caffeine content and natural flavor in the tea. As soon as the harvest is picked, the matcha is brought to the state of powder and becomes the main participant in Japanese tea ceremonies. At the same time, due to its delicate color, matcha varietal tea remains one of the main drinks in modern Japanese cuisines. Various studies conducted have proven that blue tea lowers high blood pressure, is useful in cancer and heart disease. Constantly drinking blue tea protects against heart disease. In addition, blue tea also helps brain function well. It has also been studied by scientists for the nerve-calming properties of blue tea and its reduced risk of diabetes. There may not be a person who has not heard of the Japanese tea ceremony. It was a tradition organized in a separate tea room, and the main purpose of organizing it was to show favor to the guest and help him feel a different atmosphere, albeit a little from his usual life. Nowadays, tea ceremonies have become a hobby and a means of welcoming tourists. Such ceremonies are organized in traditional Japanese gardens, hotels, or tea culture centers. Usually, formal tea ceremonies end with a cup of bitter and a cup of lightly brewed tea.

To attend the ceremony, first of all, it is necessary to choose a suitable outfit for it. In this, it is considered advisable to choose clothes that are not too stylish and quickly conspicuous, but modest and free from jewelry. Typically, the tea ceremony is held in gardens or garden-covered buildings. This environment was also chosen to stabilize a person's mental state. A well will be installed at the entrance to the room where the ceremony will take place, and the arriving guests will wash their hands from it and then go inside.

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